

COMPOUNDS OF MANGANOUS CHLORIDE WITH MONO- AND DI-AMINES

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Several complex compounds of manganous chloride have been prepared by the action of mono- and di-amines on manganous chloride in organic solvents, their properties studied and structures discussed.

Rose (*Pogg. Ann.*, 1830, 20, 148) reported the formation of hexammino manganous chloride, $Mn(NH_3)_6.Cl_2$, by passing dry ammonia gas over anhydrous manganous chloride at low temperatures. The compound on heating lost ammonia, forming the diammine, $Mn(NH_3)_2.Cl_2$.

Feldt (*Ber.*, 1894, 27, 405) prepared dihydroxylamino manganous chloride, $Mn(NH_2OH)_2.Cl_2$, by treating hot aqueous solution of manganous chloride with hydroxylamine hydrochloride and adding a further quantity of the base in alcohol.

Leeds (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1888, 3, 112) obtained dianilino manganous chloride, $Mn(C_6H_5NH_2)_2.Cl_2$, by adding an excess of aniline to a solution of manganous chloride in alcohol.

Biltz and Huttig (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1919, 109, 89) determined the dissociation pressure and curves of various ammonium derivatives of manganous chloride. Anhydrous $MnCl_2$ absorbs ammonia gas at the temperatures of solid CO_2 and alcohol to form the hexammine, $MnCl_2.6NH_3$. At 76.5° the isothermal falls a little and then remains horizontal until the composition falls to that of the diammine. The isothermal for the equilibrium,

has been determined at 229° and indicates the existence of the mono-ammine.

Zvyagintsev and Gruzinskogo (*Ind. Inst. Inn. Kisova*, 1939, 11, 79; *Khiur Referat Z.*, 1940, 12, 15) obtained the compound, $MnCl_2.(CH_3NH_2)_2.2HCl.H_2O$, by treating the concentrated manganous chloride solution with HCl and adding ethylene-diamine.

As very few compounds of manganous chloride with mono- and di-amines are reported in the literature, the present investigation has been undertaken with a view to studying the preparation and properties of some of them.

EXPERIMENTAL

The amines and manganous chloride used were of B.D.H. or Merck's 'Pure' quality, and alcohol and benzene were dehydrated and redistilled.

Anhydrous manganous chloride was prepared by passing dry HCl gas over hydrated manganous chloride at $150-60^\circ$.

Manganous chloride was dissolved in alcohol and the respective amine in benzene separately. An excess of the organic component was added to the manganous chloride

solution till the precipitation was complete. In cases where the precipitate was not obtained on mixing the solutions, it was evaporated slowly on a sand-bath when the compound separated out. The precipitate was separated by filtration, washed free of the amine and dried at the room temperature.

Manganese was estimated as $Mn_2P_2O_7$ and chlorine as $AgCl$. Solvent of crystallisation was estimated by heating the substance to a constant weight and noting down the loss in weight. The organic matter was found by difference.

TABLE I

Manganous chloride with mono- and diamines.[$MnCl_2$: amino group = 1 : 2].

Amines.	Compounds formed.	Colour.	% Manganese.		% Chlorine.		% Org. matter.	
			Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
α -Naphthylamine	Di- α -naphthylamino-M $MnCl_2 \cdot (\alpha-C_{10}H_7NH_2)_2$	White	12.84	13.32	18.05	17.20	69.11	69.48
β -Naphthylamine	Di- β -naphthylamino-M $MnCl_2 \cdot (\beta-C_{10}H_7NH_2)_2$	Violet	13.63	13.32	17.79	17.20	68.58	69.48
<i>p</i> -Toluidine	Di- <i>p</i> -toluidino-M $MnCl_2 \cdot (p-C_6H_4CH_3NH_2)_2$	White	15.60	16.15	20.59	20.84	63.81	63.03
Phenylhydrazine	Diphenylhydrazino-M $MnCl_2 \cdot (C_6H_5NH.NH_2)_2$	Brown	16.57	16.06	21.92	20.73	61.51	63.21
Ethylene-diamine	Mono-ethylenediamino-M $MnCl_2 \cdot (NH_2CH_2.CH_2NH_2)$	Grey	28.08	29.54	37.77	38.15	34.15	32.31
<i>p</i> -Phenylenediamine	Mono- <i>p</i> -phenylenediamino-M $MnCl_2 \cdot [p-C_6H_4(NH_2)_2]$	Dark violet	23.12	23.47	29.68	30.31	47.20	46.22
<i>o</i> -Phenylenediamine	Mono- <i>o</i> -phenylenediamino-M $MnCl_2 \cdot [o-C_6H_4(NH_2)_2]$	Greenish white	23.85	23.47	30.81	30.31	45.34	46.22
Benzidine	Mono-benzidino-M $MnCl_2 \cdot (NH_2C_6H_4.C_6H_4NH_2)$	Do	17.12	17.71	23.47	21.87	59.41	60.42
<i>o</i> -Dianisidine	Mono- <i>o</i> -dianisidino-M $MnCl_2 \cdot (NH_2OCH_3C_6H_3.C_6H_3CH_3ONH_2)$	Ash	15.29	14.85	19.54	19.16	65.17	65.99
<i>o</i> -Tolidine	Mono- <i>o</i> -tolidino-M $MnCl_2 \cdot (NH_2CH_2C_6H_3.C_6H_3CH_3NH_2)$	Dark grey	15.72	16.25	20.90	20.97	63.38	62.78

*M stands for manganous chloride.

DISCUSSION

According to Sidgwick ("Electronic Theory of Valency", 1927) the maximum covalency that should be exhibited by manganese is six, but no such compound in which it exhibits a covalency of '6' has so far been reported. The co-ordination number of manganese in all the cases studied is 4.

Cox *et al.* (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 1556) found by X-ray methods that manganous chloride dipyridine, $MnCl_2 \cdot Py_2$, was a 4-covalent compound, with four groups in a plane with the central atom and at the corners of the square. But by calculating Bohr magnetons, Mellor and Coryell (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 1786) assigned a structure of the octahedral ionic type with two shared edges for this compound.

It has been found that two molecules of a monoamine and one of a diamine combine with one molecule of manganous chloride and the compounds formed can be represented as $Mn(2A).Cl_2$ and $Mn(D).Cl_2$, where A = a monoamine and D = a diamine.

This shows that in none of them the E.A.N. assumes the inert gas stable configuration, but they have a symmetrical structure and, hence, they are stable.

All the compounds are stable in the dry atmosphere at the room temperature, but these hydrolyse readily on boiling with water. Most of them do not melt but decompose at high temperatures. On heating with sodalime, the corresponding amines separate out and condense on the cooler part of the test-tube. The diamino compounds are more stable than the monoamino derivatives, probably due to the formation of chelate compounds.

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